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ASSESSING ACCURACY USING THE IXELL METER FOR GLYCEMIC CONTROL IN SICK CHILDREN WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation. *Determination of blood glucose concentration -one of the most common tests performed by clinical diagnostic laboratories. In addition to various laboratory methods for measuring glucose concentration, there are a large number of portable devices - glucometers, which allow this procedure to be carried out at home. When providing medical care to patients diabetes mellitus, especially in children, the clinician must be confident that the performance of glucometers meets the analytical quality criteria necessary for safe and effective treatment. The current dilemma between analytical quality criteria established by official regulatory organizations and professional medical societies requires constant dialogue and improvement in the performance of diagnostic technologies for measuring blood glucose, especially diagnostic methods at the point of care.*

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus, glycemic control, insulin, resistance, metabolic regulation, biological factors, glucometers, glucose concentration, glycemic monitoring.*

ОЦЕНКА ТОЧНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГЛЮКОМЕТРА IXELL ДЛЯ КОНТРОЛЯ ГЛИКЕМИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ДЕТЕЙ САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ

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Аннотация. *Определение концентрации глюкозы в крови – одно из наиболее распространенных исследований, проводимых клинико-диагностическими лабораториями. Помимо различных лабораторных методов измерения концентрации глюкозы, существует большое количество портативных приборов – глюкометров, позволяющих проводить эту процедуру в домашних условиях. При оказании медицинской помощи больным сахарным диабетом, особенно детям, врач-клиницист должен быть уверен, что характеристики глюкометров соответствуют аналитическим критериям качества, необходимым для безопасного и эффективного лечения. Современная дилемма между критериями качества анализа, установленными официальными регулирующими организациями и профессиональными медицинскими обществами, требует постоянного диалога и совершенствования эффективности диагностических технологий измерения уровня глюкозы в крови, особенно методов диагностики на месте оказания медицинской помощи.*

Ключевые слова: *сахарный диабет, гликемический контроль, инсулин, резистентность, метаболическая регуляция, биологические факторы, глюкометры, концентрация глюкозы, гликемический мониторинг.*

Introduction. The influence of analytical, preanalytical and biological factors contributes to the creation of the so-called uncertainty budget, which often exceeds the requirements of medical professionals for the safe diagnosis and monitoring of diseases [2]. In accordance with the requirements of the latest version of ISO 22870, the clinical diagnostic laboratory should be responsible for the measurement of glucose using glucometers and other equipment [3].

Effective and high-quality laboratory monitoring of glycemia using diagnostic devices near the patient in everyday life is most often carried out using self-determination of glucose concentration carried out directly by patients with diabetes at home. Modern laboratory medicine recommends comparing the performance characteristics of glucometers to study the quality of their work and assess the comparability of blood glucose measurement results [4].

Target. Assessing the accuracy of a medical device Portable blood glucose meter with single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL for glycemic control in children with diabetes mellitus.

Methods. Study design. A single-center, single-stage, selective, controlled, non-randomized study was conducted. Eligibility criteria The clinical study included 105 children aged 1 month to 17 years with type 1 diabetes mellitus diagnosed in accordance with the standards of medical care for patients with diabetes mellitus (2019) [5]. All patients were examined in a specialized endocrinology hospital; the basic diagnostic complex, in addition to the assessment of medical history and physical examination methods, included a daily glycemic profile and determination of glycosylated hemoglobin. Indicators of glycosylated hemoglobin were 7-11%, the concentration of glucose in the blood fluctuated within 2.5-27.5 mmol/l.

Glycemic parameters were assessed during dynamic monitoring of patients undergoing hospital treatment for 3 to 7 days. All patients received insulin therapy and did not have significant metabolic imbalances (decompensated ketoacidosis). Duration of the study. Patients were recruited from 07/01/23 to 08/31/23. Description of medical intervention. In all patients, glycemia was determined in the same drop of capillary blood using the tested IXELL glucometer and the SUPER GL laboratory glucose and lactate analyzer (in vitro diagnostics). To assess the accuracy of the readings, the manufacturer provided portable blood glucose concentration meters with a single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL (included in the state register of measuring instruments (registration number 46361-11)) and test strips of three different series. The IXELL glucometer works on the principle of glucose oxidase measurement and calibrated using

whole capillary blood [6]. Indicators obtained using the automatic glucose and lactate analyzer SUPER GL (Germany) were taken as reference values. The SUPER GL automatic analyzer is designed for serial research and has the function of measuring emergency samples. The operating principle of the analyzer is electrochemical and is calibrated using whole capillary blood. Main outcome of the study Acceptability of measurement error limits glycemia with a portable blood glucose concentration meter with a single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL in accordance with the requirements Ethical review All patients over 15 years of age and parents of patients under 15 years of age gave informed written voluntary consent to participate in this study.

The results of the entire accuracy measurement interval of the IXELL system are presented graphically in Fig. 3 and in table. 4. The lowest reference glucose value is <5.55 mmol/l with an interval of ± 0.83 mmol/l, the highest is ≥ 5.55 mmol/l with an interval of $\pm 15\%$. The total number of acceptable values was 639 out of 660, therefore 96.8% of the values were within the system's accuracy criteria. Additional Study Findings All capillary blood samples replaced with modified samples in which glucose concentrations were increased or decreased to achieve the required distribution were included in the total number of study samples (n=660). Adverse events When conducting a study of adverse events no phenomena were recorded.

Discussion. Summary of the main result of the study The ability of analytical functional characteristics was verified and accuracy criteria of the medical device were established. A portable blood glucose concentration meter with a single-use electrochemical strip PKG-03 IXELL, allowing its use for glycemetic control in children with diabetes mellitus.

Discussion of the main result of the study According to the recommendations for monitoring the control of carbohydrate metabolism (ISPAD, 2018), pediatric patients on intensified insulin therapy or insulin pump therapy are recommended to conduct glycemetic testing 6 to 10 times a day. The number of studies may increase when selecting the dose of insulin during the period of decompensation of diabetes mellitus, during stress, intercurrent illnesses and physical activity. For self-monitoring of blood glucose concentrations, it is recommended to use glucometers intended for individual use. Personal blood glucose meters must comply GOST R ISO 15197-2015 for analytical and clinical accuracy.

Glycemetic control in diabetes mellitus, especially in children, requires fairly high accuracy of portable measurement devices glucose. This study provided data

to evaluate the accuracy of the IXELL blood glucose meter in pediatric patients with diabetes mellitus. The new criteria require that 99% of results be in zones A and B of the Harmonized Error Grid for Type I Diabetes [7]. This is an allowance for the fact that manual glucose measurements using modern portable glucose meters are still sensitive to the user's technique. Since it would be unreasonable to expect a match in 100% of cases, the presence of 1% outliers is accepted. In the study, 100% were in zones A and B, i.e. zones of clinically accurate results and safe deviations. Similar data were obtained in adult patients, both in a state of ketoacidosis and without acid-base imbalance [6, 8]. When analyzing the system accuracy results in individual blood glucose concentration intervals, 96.8% (>95%) deviations of the IXELL glucometer readings from the reference values correspond to the zones of clinically correct and safe deviations.

Medical experts have long been calling for more accurate blood glucose measurements. Back in 1987, the American Diabetes Association recommended: “The goal of all future self-testing blood glucose systems will be to achieve <10% variability at glucose concentrations of 30–400 mg/dL 100% of the time” [9]. It is logical to assume that more accurate glucose meters will lead to more accurate insulin dosing and therefore more favorable outcomes. But current meter technology has reached the limit of its analytical performance capabilities, and the development of more accurate glucose meters may result in less usability for patients.

Conclusion. The study showed that the use of the IXELL glucometer in real clinical practice allows for high-quality glycemic control and is safe for pediatric patients from 1 month to 17 years.

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Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyligi uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.